

Incredible Active Region 1429: One for the record books

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On March 2, 2012, Active Region (AR) 1429 rotated onto the Earth-facing solar disk. For about 27 days (roughly one solar rotation period), it was in continual activity, producing large eruptions such as solar flares and coronal mass ejections (CMEs), two of the most energetic/catastrophic solar phenomena.

Solar flares represent one type of solar eruptive event, appearing as a sudden brightening on the sun's surface. For a powerful solar flare event, the radiation energy is on the order of 10^{25} Joule. Such flares radiate throughout the whole broad electromagnetic spectrum, from gamma rays to x-rays, through the ultraviolet (UV) wavelength, visible light to kilometer-long radio waves. Flares are usually measured in terms of Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) and x-ray intensity as flare effects are more pronounced at these wavelengths.

Within minutes of the flares, radio blackout can occur when solar flares modify the composition and structure of the sunlit side ionosphere, producing sudden ionospheric disturbances. Radio communication can be affected, since the ionosphere serves as the medium through which the signals propagate. In addition, radio noises/bursts associated with a solar flare event can affect radio communication and the GPS (Global Positioning System) directly. For example, solar radio bursts on December 6, 2006 affected the operation of many of GPS receivers [Cerruti et al., 2008]. Flares also contribute to the flux enhancement of solar energetic particles (SEPs), with the associated radiation posing a major threat to spacecraft and human safety in space. A high level of SEPs can cause radio communication problems at the polar region, affecting airline operations.

Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) are a second major type of solar eruption that can have significant space weather/societal consequences. CMEs cause intense geomagnetic storms and drive fast mode shocks that accelerate charged particles. Enhanced radiation levels both of ions and electrons can result, posing dangers to humans and to technological assets in space. CMEs are also the major culprit in generating large amplitude Geomagnetically Induced Currents (GICs), which are a source of concern for power grid safety.

In total, there were ten major solar events originating from the region if we count the two CMEs occurring in quick succession on March 7, 2012 as one. The CME speed during these events all exceeded 1100 km/s while the average speed of CMEs typically clocks in at around 500 km/s.

Events in the Earth-facing Solar Disk

During the period of March 2 to March 15, as it rotated from the uttermost east limb to the uttermost west limb, the solar disk fired off 32 C class flares, 15 M class flares and 3 X class flares ('C' for 'common', 'M' for 'Moderate', 'X' for 'Extreme'). All three X-class flares (on March 5 and 7 in universal time) were accompanied by very fast/wide CMEs. Here is our detailed summary video of the 2 X class flares/two CMEs that occurred on March 7, 2012:

<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HeoKf6NfEJI&feature=youtu.be>.

The M-class flares from the region that occurred on March 4, March 9, March 10 and March 13 were just as dramatic. Each produced a fast and wide CME with speeds exceeding 1100 km/s. That is more than two times the average speed of CMEs, which typically clock in at around 500 km/s.

The location/rotation of the active region and its major flares/CMEs can be seen here on our integrated space weather analysis system (iSWA) while it was in the field of view of the NASA mission SDO, standing for Solar Dynamics Observatory.

iSWA is a web-based, user configurable information system that provides highly diverse and distributed space weather products, consisting of the latest observational data along with the most advanced space weather model simulation output (<http://iswa.gsfc.nasa.gov>). iSWA tools and products have enabled successful operation of the NASA Goddard Space Weather Center (<http://swc.gsfc.nasa.gov/main/>), whose primary objective is to provide latest space weather information and forecast to all NASA robotic mission operators and partners, and to bring space weather knowledge to the public.

Here is an iSWA layout showing the major Earth-facing events, also providing a glimpse to what iSWA is capable of, one of which is to save any layout of user interest (be an event or a series of events or any configuration) to enable sharing. Detailed description of the layout is provided in the Appendix.

http://bit.ly/laptop_layout_Earthside

Figure 1 shows the flares from the six major Earth-facing solar events in SDO AIA (Atmospheric Imaging Assembly) images at the 131Å (Angstrom) wavelength, which is suitable for viewing regions where flares are occurring. The rotation of the active region 1429 across the Earth facing solar disk is evident here.

Our large-scale heliospheric model of CMEs (WSA+ENLIL+Cone) [e.g., *Odstrcil et al.*, 2004, 2005; *Taktakishvili et al.*, 2009, 2010] enables us, both scientifically and operationally, to view these massive outflows from the sun as they travel through interplanetary space. Our forecasts of the time arrival at different objects of interest were generally close to the actual observations. The corresponding CMEs for each event are shown in Figure 2. What is displayed is the simulated color-coded proton density (scaled to 1 AU) in the equatorial plane with its radial distance of 2 AU (the

Sun is in the center), where the compressed-density regions due to CME propagation and the low-density regions behind the CME front can be seen. Black-white dashed lines indicate the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) lines connecting to various spacecraft. Different spacecraft are shown as rectangles of different colors, while planets are marked by color-coded ovals.

For CMEs heading in the direction of earth, our space weather alerts also estimate the impact in terms of geomagnetic activity.

Farside Events

On March 16, the active region finally rotated off the Earth-facing solar disk. But the action didn't stop there. During the period of March 18 and March 26, four sizable backside CMEs with blistering speeds, respectively, of 1450 km/s, 1550 km/s, 1600 km/s and 1450 km/s erupted. These events occurred around 00:39 UT on March 18, 07:39 UT on March 21, 00:39 UT on March 24, and 23:12 UT on March 26.

Consequently, the energetic proton radiation level at STEREO A was elevated almost immediately following the onset of the first three events and the proton radiation level at STEREO B started to increase compared to the previous two events due to AR1429's relative location to STEREO A and STEREO B spacecraft and magnetic connectivity.

The four events can be viewed with the help of STEREO A and STEREO B EUVI (Extreme UltraViolet Imager) 195 Å images, with the first two in the field of view of STEREO A and the last two in that of STEREO B.

Here is an iSWA layout showing the major far side events. The detailed description of the layout can be found in the Appendix.

http://bit.ly/1429_backside_majorevents

Figure 3 shows the STEREO A/B EUVI images on the top, where the red arrow is used to indicate the flare/activity site. The corresponding simulated CMEs for each of the four backside events are shown at the bottom, in the same format as those in Figure 2.

If these back-facing solar events had been measured in the same way as the Earth-facing ones, the flares associated with them would have been recorded as quite intense, probably placing them in the M-class range.

Though a CME's propagation direction is not linearly correlated with its initial location (the location of the active region), its temporal evolution with the active region is evident from our predictive model results.

In addition to these four major backside events, a few more flare/CME events took place in association with AR 1429 while it was on the far side of the Sun. One occurred around 04:45 UT on March 25, 2012, with a CME speed of ~700 km/s, and two successive CMEs occurred on March 28 with first one starting around 01:25 UT

at a speed of 620 km/s and the second one starting around 01:48 UT at a speed of 1035 km/s. For a more complete display of the backside events, please check out this iSWA layout: http://bit.ly/AR1429_backside_allevents

Again, details can be found in the Appendix.

Summary

In summary, 10 major CMEs (10 in total if counting the two CMEs occurring in quick succession on March 7, 2012 as one) occurred from March 4th to March 26 in association with the active region (AR 1429). The region has produced CMEs with their propagation direction spreading over 360 degree of the Sun.

Here is our YouTube movie summarizing the major events from AR 1429.
<http://youtu.be/PbyJswbX4VA>

The active region's long duration and seemingly dangerous appearance didn't translate into the severe space weather impacts that many had feared. Nevertheless, it has dominated space weather conditions throughout the solar system for more than three weeks, a little shy of one solar rotation (about 27 days).

For the energetic proton radiation, which generally tends to be broad in space when associated with a flare and a CME pair, the peak impact was at STEREO B first. Then it rotated to Earth, reached STEREO A and then finally returned to STEREO B. Two major episodes of energetic proton radiation enhancement in the near-Earth space were due to the solar activities on March 7 and March 13.

For Earth, the strongest space weather impacts were due to the two-X class flare/CMEs activities on March 7. The geomagnetic activity level index Kp reached 7 from 06-12 UT (1 AM – 7AM ET) on March 9 on a scale from 0 to 9, while the energetic proton radiation level for the greater than 10 MeV particles was the highest since October 2003.

Other periods of enhanced geomagnetic activity when Kp reached 6 were on March 7, March 12 and March 15. In all three cases, the enhanced activity can be attributed to the CME interaction with Earth's environment. The corresponding CMEs were associated with the X1.1 class flare on March 4, the M8.4 class flare on March 10 and the M7.9 class flare on March 13 respectively. The flurry of activity has also boosted Earth's radiation belt energetic electron fluxes since March 10.

Mesmerizing observers for a period spanning a solar rotation, Active Region 1429 has certainly kept people involved in space weather operations busy, in addition to stirring up a media sensation. Meanwhile, the long-lasting nature of its activities may give us a new glimpse into the inner workings of solar activities that are the major and ultimate source of space weather. Active Region 1429 is unique, unprecedented and record-setting in the sense that it is the best observed sunspot on record. In comparison to previous active regions of comparable size and longevity, its associated space weather activities were tracked 360 degrees around

the Sun with unparallel spatial and temporal resolution enabled by STEREO and SDO spacecraft. Such a degree of tracking was not available for any previous Active Regions of similar caliber. Hopefully, the wealth of data collected from NASA and other missions during this period can help us unlock many hidden secrets of space weather.

On March 28, leading solar physicist Dr Gopalswamy called for an international campaign to observe, track, model and analyze the space weather impacts of all the solar events that happened during the interval of March 29 to April 30, 2012. Even though solar activities from this active region have gradually wound down, the campaign effort promises to yield significant research results.

Other relevant links:

iSWA is the Integrated Space Weather Analysis system:

<http://iswa.ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov>

NASA Space Weather Center facebook page:

<http://www.facebook.com/nasaswc>

The NASA Space Weather Center website:

<http://swc.gsfc.nasa.gov/main/>

Appendix

iSWA Layout 1: Six Major Earth-Facing Events

http://bit.ly/laptop_layout_Earthside

From top to bottom, what is shown here is the iSWA interactive timeline tool with the flare intensity (in the unit of Watts/m²) in the 1-8 Angstrom (Å) x-ray wavelength measured at GOES is in black (this has been used as the conventional way of classifying solar flares), the 13-100 MeV proton flux at STEREO A in blue and STEREO B in red in the unit of pfu/MeV (pfu stands for particle flux unit=1/cm²/s/sr), the greater than 10 MeV proton integral flux at GOES (at geosynchronous orbit) in yellow/orange and the greater than 100 MeV proton integral flux at GOES in green.

What follows next is the SDO EVE MEGS-SAM images (Woods et al., 2012) in the 1-7 Å wavelength band for the sixth major Earth-facing events, with flares appearing as bright/saturated white spots. The one on March 13 is substituted with the SDO/AIA 131 Å image since the SDO EVE MEGS-SAM imager was in calibration mode.

The simulation results of the accompanying CMEs from our real-time space weather operations are shown next.

SDO/AIA 131 Å images of the events (particularly the flare features) are shown at the end.

All image-based iSWA products can be displayed in either still or movie mode. The movie mode provides the dynamical characterization of the events.

iSWA Layout 2: Four Major Farside Events

http://bit.ly/1429_backside_majorevents

The layout starts with the interactive timeline showing the radiation intensity due to SEPs (Solar Energetic Particles) at different spacecraft location. The >100 MeV integral proton flux at GOES (at geosynchronous orbit) is in black, the >10 MeV integral proton flux at GOES in blue, the 13-100 MeV proton flux at STEREO A in red and STEREO B in orange. The temporal evolution of the intensity at different spacecraft in relevance with the activity location can be seen.

STEREO EUVI images at 195 Å are shown next for the four events, followed by the CME simulation results of the events.

Coronagraph images of the CMEs from the four events are displayed at the end, each with views from three different spacecraft (in the order of STEREO B, SOHO, and STEREO A).

iSWA Layout 3: Four Major Farside Events

http://bit.ly/AR1429_backside_allevents

This layout is similar to Layout #2 except it shows two additional space weather events (weaker than the four major ones) while the active region was in the farside.

The layout starts out with the SEP fluxes at different spacecraft locations, followed by STEREO EUVI images at 195 Å, with the first two in the field of view of STEREO B and the last four in the field of view of STEREO B. Next it shows the CME simulations of all six far side events. The coronagraph images of two slower CME events (occurred on March 25 and March 28 respectively) are displayed at the bottom of the layout.

References:

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